

TEACHING PETROLEUM SPECIFIED ENGLISH TO STUDENTS

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Abstract. *A fundamental change in the target formulation of learning a foreign language is associated with the further humanization of higher education, strengthening the principle of a student-centered approach. The professional trend of teaching students of non-linguistic universities a foreign language is preserved, but acquires other essential characteristics. The narrow professional trends and specialized bias in teaching students of non-linguistic universities in a foreign language is replaced by a general professional / general scientific way of the discipline "Foreign Language" with the need to teach students how to work independently to master personally significant foreign language content. In this regard, the urgent task of developing methodological support for such a learning process is currently being set. Thus, it is possible to present a model of professionally-oriented teaching of a foreign language to students of higher education studying in the specialty of petroleum business.*

Keywords: *professionally oriented, model of teaching, petroleum industry, specified terminology, higher education, English for Specific Purposes, English as a Foreign Language.*

INTRODUCTION

For all non-linguistic specialties, a competence is formulated that fixes the requirement for the results of learning a foreign language. It belongs to the group of general cultural competencies and implies the ability of the graduate "to communicate in oral and written forms in Uzbek, Russian and/or foreign languages to solve the problems of interpersonal and intercultural interaction, this goal does not postulate the professional orientation of the process of teaching students of non-linguistic universities a foreign language, which inevitably leads to a change in the content, means and methods of teaching.

A fundamental change in the target formulation of learning a foreign language is associated with the further humanization of higher education, strengthening the principle of a student-centered approach. The global goal of education is the formation of a responsible autonomous personality capable of making decisions in the conditions of choice. The simple accumulation of knowledge, skills and abilities is no longer relevant in the modern era of computerization due to the multiple increase in the volume and speed of new information flows. In the hierarchy of didactic goals, the general educational setting approaches in importance the practical one: "The most important task of a teacher is not so much to teach students their subject, but above all, to teach them to learn, to master the basic methods of cognition for the independent acquisition of the necessary knowledge" [4; 336 p]. University graduates do not need deep immersion in a narrow professional environment, but, above all, a developed ability to master new segments of the professional sphere with the help of general educational skills. In this regard, the narrow professional orientation of teaching students of non-linguistic universities in a foreign language is replaced by a general professional / general scientific way.

Most of the Educational Standards of Higher Education, unlike the standards of the previous generation require a narrow professional way in teaching students of non-linguistic universities a foreign language.

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Back in 2016, in Uzbekistan, when teaching a foreign language in higher educational institutions, when training non-linguistic specialists, there was a tendency to teach the language for general purposes. But as changes are introduced in the field of personnel needs and in their training at the world level, the requirements began to change and now the standards require specialists to know the language not only at the level of general communication, but also its knowledge, taking into account the specialization of terminology. Although, when training specialists from various industries, it is necessary to take into account the specialty of the trained personnel and create manuals in their areas using materials on the specialty, paying special attention to terminology.

METHODS

From the ideas given the above, we can cite as an example the students in the oil and gas field of training. Until 2015 - 2017, the goal for students was to learn the language for general purposes and the textbooks used ranged from IELTS preparation to HEADWAY. Then, in a pilot mode, it was decided to introduce teaching aids of an even narrower focus, such as English for oil and gas engineers.

In the works of domestic methodologists and linguists, teaching a foreign language of a specialty is more often defined by the term "professional-oriented teaching of a foreign language". This term was used in dissertations of a number of scientific schools: T. S. Serova, I. L. Bim, S. G. Ter-Minasova, N. N. Sergeeva, I. A. Giniatullina and many others. Following the representatives of the national methodological schools, we consider professionally directed teaching of a foreign language in a non-linguistic university to be broader than the study of a foreign language for special purposes. The basis of professionally directed teaching of a foreign language is its integration with special disciplines in order to obtain a synergistic effect, as a result of which students receive additional professional knowledge and form the necessary professional qualities of a person.

RESULTS

In a non-linguistic university, the formation of foreign language communicative competence in the field of professional activity has its own specifics and, according to the definition of N. N. Sergeeva, represents "a set of knowledge about native and foreign culture, skills and abilities to understand and adequately use professional vocabulary in speech, correctly apply knowledge about the culture of native speakers in professionally oriented situations of communication and the ability to effectively participate in professional intercultural interaction with foreign colleagues "[6, c. 150].

Before you start creating a teaching manual for English for Petroleum Industry (the initial stage of training), it is necessary to identify the difficulties that trainees may encounter. These difficulties should be reduced or eliminated as far as possible. The objective difficulties include the following.

1. Joint groups, including students who studied Russian or Uzbek as their first foreign language. The negative impact of interlingual interference.

2. The specifics of the English pronunciation and reading rules, which differ significantly from the Russian and Uzbek rules. The presence of sounds that do not exist in other languages, the linking and cohesion of sounds, rhythmic groups.

3. Features of English grammar: the presence of agreements, multiple uses of articles, a complex system of tenses of verbs and sequence of tenses, features of the configuration of verbs of the third group.

4. The specifics of the English professional lexicon and terminological dictionary in the specialty.

5. Use of authentic professionally directed texts and topics of oral communication.

6. Strictly regulated according to certain rules, globally accepted norms, measures, trends and events concerned with petroleum activities.

7. Accounting for cultural traditions and characteristics in the petroleum business.

8. A clear system of petroleum combinations.

The difficulties of a subjective nature include the lack of special knowledge of petroleum business among foreign language teachers, lack of knowledge of modern English realities in this professional field, significant time spent on searching for authentic materials in the specialty, their processing and adaptation, the need for advice from petroleum business professionals.

It also requires a special approach to the selection of training content. It should reflect the latest scientific achievements in the field of petroleum business in order to provide trainees with opportunities for professional growth. The content of the course is presented as a set of competencies that students must learn in the teaching process.

Let us consider the structure of the content of the textbook being developed, using the components of the model of professionally directed teaching of a foreign language by D. L. Matukhin [5, p. 121-129].

1. **Communication** skills by types of speech activity, based on general and professional vocabulary. Teaching speaking at the initial stage involves the development of *dialogic* skills, skills of *spontaneous expression*, *production* of a *monologue* [2, p. 3], the ability to *talk* about everyday topics and *communicate* in situations related to the petroleum industry.

The purpose of teaching listening is to acquire the skills of perception and understanding of English speech in a *monologue* or *dialogic* form in the field of everyday and professional communication. The nature and goals of professionally directed listening became the basis for the use of its various subspecies [5, p. 10]: tentative-introductory, tentative-evaluative, informative-selective and informative-activity.

Teaching **reading** aims to develop the skills to master various types of reading *publications*, especially special literature. The studies of T.S. Serova indicate that professionally directed reading is aimed at the future profession, at the formation of *professional competence*, therefore, it has specific characteristics and functions [6, p. 10]. The student, as a future petroleum service specialist, determines his motives, goals and preferences in choosing special literature that

has consumer value. Among the important functions of this type of reading are *cognitive, communicative, referential* (nomination field), *informational* (predication field), *creative* and *instrumental* [6, p. 10]. Considering these facts, we selected texts of a professional orientation and authentic publications of various functional styles and genres: *excerpts from scientific articles, historical references, newspaper ads, brochures, recipes, poems and rhymes, proverbs and sayings on the specific topic.*

The result of learning to **write** is the acquisition of the communicative competence required for written communication in the framework of professional activities in the petroleum business. Students must be taught, first of all, the ability to compose their resume (CV) and a motivation letter for employment, annotate and summarize the information received, as well as translate professionally significant texts from English into Russian and from Russian into a foreign language.

2. The next component is language knowledge and skills, which are an integral part of complex communication skills. They are represented by the phonetic phenomena of the English language, its main grammatical forms, word formation rules, the necessary lexical and terminological minimum, selected in accordance with the situations and topics of professional communication, in order to master the communicative competencies defined by the program of training in petroleum business.

When selecting language material, the specifics of this professional field are taken into account: petroleum service terminology, conceptual base, lexical and syntactic features (interrogative sentences, prepositional constructions, abbreviations, compound nouns), grammatical features (verb tenses, conditional verbs, passive form, impersonal phrases, gender and number of nouns and adjectives, degrees of comparison of adjectives and adverbs, continuous articles, pronouns).

3. Sociocultural knowledge is represented by regional and linguistic regional knowledge. Regional knowledge includes encyclopedic, background knowledge and knowledge of the realities of the country, necessary in order to become a competent user of the English language, since the goal of training is not only communication in a foreign language, but also readiness, as well as the ability to conduct a dialogue of cultures. Linguistic and cultural knowledge is represented by lexical knowledge that reflects the culture of English in the semantics of language units.

4. Learning skills, rational methods and techniques of mental activity that can provide a culture of learning English as a second foreign language in the learning process in artificial communicative situations and a culture of communication with English speakers in real professional communication. According to I. A. Zimnyaya, the competence of cognitive activity is “setting and solving cognitive problems, non-standard solutions, problem situations - their creation and resolution, productive and reproductive cognition, research, intellectual activity”.

DISCUSSION

Depending on the content of future professional activity, the educational process is dominated by such forms that contribute to the realization of the main goal - the formation of foreign language communicative competence. Taking into account this fact, the training manual presents a system of exercises that have a different degree of communicative freedom for students:

- substitution exercises, in which actions are proposed by analogy with the sample;
- transformational exercises, where students apply already existing knowledge and skills in a changed context or other communicative situation;

- conditionally communicative tasks, where students participate in communicative situations that imitate real professional communication, but follow the instructions of the textbook;
- creative communication tasks, where communication is carried out in English within the framework of topics related to petroleum industry.

Additional means of forming media literacy of students of the specialty through the study of English is participation in scientific and practical conferences, competitions of research works devoted to the study of the language aspects of professional activity. So, in the 2015-16 academic year, within the framework of the discipline "Foreign Language", the research work "Peculiarities of speech impact in the advertising text" was prepared for participation in the student's scientific and practical conference of the university. According to the results of the study, strategies and tactics of speech influence in the advertising text were identified and described based on the material of the English-language advertising of deodorants.

Thus, it is possible to present a model of professionally-oriented teaching of a foreign language to students of higher education studying in the specialty of petroleum business (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Model of professionally oriented EFL teaching in petroleum field.

CONCLUSION

After analyzing this model, we can conclude that the formation of foreign language communicative competences and the development of components of media competences are interdependent. Classes in the discipline of "Foreign Language" include a variety of creative tasks that help deepen students' knowledge of the media and acquire new ones that help increase the level of IT competences and foreign language communicative competences of students on the material of English-language media texts. The presented model, in combination with the

development of media competence and the study of English, seems to be successful in the context of professional media education.

In order to control the process of assimilation of the material, test tasks, lexical and grammatical tests, creative tasks, drawing up dialogues for certain situations of petroleum specified teaching activities, writing short reports/ letters/forms/cards/notes and etc., and developing special CVs are offered.

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